
THE THEME OF EDUCATION IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE

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Gafurova D.T

3 rd year student.

Kurbanova M.O

Scientific adviser

Ferghana state university.

Abstract.

The article is devoted to the problem of education in Russian classical literature.

Key words.

literature, learning, education, upbringing...

Аннотация.

Работа посвящена проблеме воспитания в русской классической литературе.

Ключевые слова.

литература, обучение, образование, воспитание...

At school, teachers in literature lessons pay special attention to the topic of spiritual and moral education. This is not accidental, because education is the foundation on which the whole future life of a person is built. Literature is one of the most important subjects in the life of any student - on the examples of the fate of literary heroes, he often builds his life. Literature develops imagination, logical thinking, the ability to speak beautifully, aesthetic taste - it is on all this, and not only, that the upbringing of a person is built. Mastering the literary classics by students is an indispensable condition for maintaining the unity of national culture.

The formation of a morally active personality is the main task of teaching and educating in literature lessons. The book plays a huge role in the education, upbringing and development of the child. It is books that teach us from childhood to do good deeds and not to do bad ones. In childhood, experiences are especially acute, and the mind is not yet sufficiently prepared to correctly assess everything that is happening around. The role of the book in the upbringing of the student is enormous. Book is a textbook of morality, a source of knowledge, a friendly interlocutor and, of course, a best friend.

The role of Russian classical literature in the education of schoolchildren is quite large. Reading classic books, children get acquainted with the past of our

Motherland, with the life and way of life of our ancestors, with the history and geography of the country.

As a result of this, they begin to realize themselves as the successors of everything created on earth and the successors of the deeds of their ancestors, responsible for the fate of the planet. Later they will understand that without the past there can be neither present nor future.

"I owe everything good in myself to books,"¹ said Maxim Gorky. The book opened the great writer's eyes to the big world, taught him to recognize good and bad in the surrounding reality, in people, inspired him to fight against everything unworthy and immoral.

Education is designed to form personal values and guidelines, attitudes and worldview. Turning to the works of Russian classical literature allows us to see with our own eyes the mistakes adults made in raising children, and the obvious consequences of these mistakes.

Skimming through the pages of the school curriculum, you involuntarily pay attention to the comedy of D.I. Fonvizin "Undergrowth". This play is especially valuable for youth, it can help young people in choosing a worthy life path. In Fonvizin's comedy, the theme of education is expressed in the confrontation between good and evil, meanness and nobility, sincerity and hypocrisy, bestiality and high spirituality. In comedy, two worlds collide with different needs, styles of life and speech patterns, with different ideals. The ideals of the heroes are clearly visible in the way they want to see their children. Let's remember Prostakov at Mitrofanushka's lesson: "Prostakov. He's lying, my dear friend! Found money, didn't share it with anyone. Take everything for yourself, Mitrofanushka.

Do not study this bad science!" [2.]

And now let's compare this with the scene where Starodum speaks to Sophia: "Starodum. According to my calculation, not the rich one who counts out money to hide it in a chest, but the one who counts out too much from himself in order to help someone who does not have what he needs.

<...>. A nobleman, for example, would consider it a first dishonor not to do anything when he has so much to do: there are people to help, there is a Fatherland to serve.

Mitrofanushka, "the fruit of malevolence," who absorbed, like a sponge, the vices of his mother, Mrs. Prostakova, he even, to some extent, surpasses her in his callousness and cruelty. The work clearly shows the difference between good and

evil, nobility and ignorance, the reader has the opportunity to evaluate all these qualities, to conclude what is truly valuable in life.

The main question asked by N.V. Gogol in the poem "Dead Souls", "Is there something bright in this world, at least some kind of appeal to the light?". The main educational idea of the work can be called the doctrine of the moral and spiritual values of a person, as opposed to material values. The father of the protagonist of Gogol's poem Chichikov conveyed to his son the instruction that Chichikov follows throughout his life: "And most of all, take care and love a penny ... ". As you can see, Chichikov was inspired from childhood with the idea that material values are more important than spiritual ones, which determines his actions in adulthood.

Another striking example of a work in which the problem of education is revealed can be considered the epic novel "War and Peace" by L.N. Tolstoy. Here Natasha Rostova touchingly takes care of her mother, who was under great stress due to the death son of Peter. The countess immediately turned into an old woman. Natasha never left her mother's side. "She alone could keep her mother from insane despair. For three weeks, Natasha lived hopelessly with her mother, slept in an armchair in her room, gave her water, fed her and, without ceasing, talked to her - she spoke, because one gentle, caressing voice calmed the countess.

Love and devotion to her mother, as we can see, makes Natasha stronger spiritually and physically, she finds energy in herself in order to support and help a loved one. This is not surprising, because love, attention and care have always reigned in the Rostov family. When the time comes, children begin to take care of their parents, as they once took care of them. There have never been conflicts, mutual hostility and hatred in the Rostov family.

In the autobiographical work of M. Gorky "Childhood", the protagonist, after the death of his father, returns to his grandfather's house with his mother. In this house, he is faced with cruelty, injustice. Children here grow up in an atmosphere of anger and hatred. They are beaten even for minor infractions. Grandfather adheres to this principle "education", despotic and completely non-pedagogical. The children did not feel any love and attention from anyone. Only the grandmother showed love, care and attention to the main character - Alyosha, who, after a lapse of time, remembers only her with a kind word. Grandfather, at the end of his life, was forced to beg. Despite the fact that he had a large family, no one wanted to take care of him, since his grandfather himself never showed kindness towards his loved ones. "... when the grandmother had already calmed down forever, the grandfather himself walked the streets of the city beggarly and insane,

pitifully begging under the windows: - My good cooks, give me a piece of a pie, I would like a pie! Oh you-and"[3].

You can compare the atmosphere in the Kashirin family from "Childhood" of Gorky and Rostovs from the novel "War and Peace" by Tolstoy. The difference is huge! The point is not only that the Rostov family did not know the need, but that mutual love and respect reigned in the Rostov family, which was not the case in the family of little Alyosha. Raising children is a very, very difficult task, it is impossible not to agree with this. Every adult is simply obliged not only to love and respect his child, but also to provide him with the opportunity to realize his aspirations through the freedom offered to him, because without it the child will grow up weak, fearful, weak-willed.

This is exactly what happened to the main character of the novel, I.A. Goncharov "Oblomov". After reading the pages of the novel, which describes the childhood of little Oblomov, we can say that it was happy and carefree. Parents loved their the boy and surrounded him with attention and care. There was one problem - Ilya was not given the opportunity to prove himself in any way. He could not take a single step on his own, was deprived of the opportunity to learn something new, to show his desires and abilities.

The tales that the nanny told him became the only possible reality for Oblomov, since he did not know or see anything else in life. This daydreaming did him a disservice, since he only knew how to dream, but never learned to act. Real life passed by, while he spent whole days in useless dreams. Only his parents are to blame for the fact that he became like this, because they did not give him the opportunity to feel independent In adult life, Oblomov is shown the way his childhood was formed - sluggish, lack of initiative. Stolz's father, on the contrary, tried to instill in his son respect for knowledge, the habit of thinking and studying. And we see how in adult life Stolz will show thriftiness, a thirst for constant activity. Stolz is trying to wrest his friend Ilya Ilyich from the clutches of Oblomovism, to awaken in him all the best feelings: kindness, honesty, sincerity, nobility, hoping that these feelings will make his life whole and harmonious. It is no coincidence that I cite literary works that are now part of the school curriculum as an example, since, in my opinion, the moral education of a person begins and ends precisely in literature lessons.

One involuntarily recalls the words of S. Smiles: "Books are the best companions of old age, at the same time they are the best leaders of youth."

Literature, real literature that makes you think, has always played a huge educational role. I believe that modern teachers are simply obliged to instill in the child a love of literature in order to educate him in an educated, intelligent personality.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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